

A large, stylized graphic of a plant branch with several green leaves, curving across the page. The branch is a light green color, and the leaves are a darker green. The branch starts from the bottom left and curves upwards and to the right, ending near the top right. The leaves are scattered along the branch.

ISLANDR Roadmap

Part 1: Introduction and common building blocks

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Summary

This deliverable gives a summary description of the ISLANDR Roadmap and its components. The ISLANDR Roadmap is a decision-making tool designed to support users engaged in contaminated site management and land redevelopment. Recognising the complexity of the remediation process, the roadmap does not prescribe a rigid set of steps but instead offers structured guidance to navigate key decisions. While it cannot map every possible choice in advance, it provides a clear direction to help users make informed and effective decisions. Adaptable to different contexts, the roadmap can be tailored to deliver user-specific insights, ensuring relevance and practical value for diverse remediation projects. The Roadmap consists of three journeys: single sites, portfolio of sites and diffuse soil contamination, and those journeys are described in separate reports.

Keywords

Sustainable Risk-based Land Management, contaminated sites, brownfields, soil health, circularity, low input remediation, contaminants of emerging concern, wider benefits, wider value, spatial planning, ISLANDR Roadmap

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CEC	Contaminants of emerging concern
CSM	Conceptual Site Model
PRA.MS	Preliminary Risk Assessment Model for the identification and assessment of problem areas for Soil contamination in Europe European Commission
SPR	Source, pathway, receptor

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ISLANDR project in brief

The Information-based Strategies for Land Remediation, in short ISLANDR, is a multidisciplinary project, which is foremost aimed at supporting the execution of the EU mission: A Soil Deal for Europe.

More specifically, the ISLANDR research activities are designed to provide tools and methods so as to support: (1) the delineation of polluted soils across Europe, (2) an evidence-based assessment of the risks posed by polluted soils, (3) the promotion of sustainable and risk-based land management practices, (4) the inclusion of a wider valuation approach in financial and investment cases, and (5) a closer integration of land contamination and spatial planning decision-making. Lessons learnt and experience gained throughout the project duration will be used to (6) deliver key policy-relevant findings related to the Soil Strategy, the new Soil Health Law, and other areas of policy where soils are crucial.

In order to road-test the project's findings, seven test areas across Europe have been identified. To begin with, the ISLANDR Test Areas (ITAs) will provide a real-world context for the planned research activities. More concretely, the ITAs have been selected to cover different land use types, such as urban, peri-urban, rural, agro-forestry, mining, wetlands and coastal areas. Furthermore, the ITAs are characterized by both point source and diffuse pollution, as well as by different soil pollution types, such as organic, inorganic, as well as contaminants of emerging concern.

Furthermore, ISLANDR brings a dedicated focus to low input remediation, by including test areas impacted by the consequences of the green transition, such as former mining areas. This will ensure that soil remediation will be facilitated even when the cost of remediation is economically marginal or may even be negative. On the one hand, this necessitates a more thorough understanding of low input remediation approaches from a technological perspective, yet it also requires a wider value proposition for investment cases and financial planning.

Key actors, stakeholders and end-beneficiaries are at the epicentre of ISLANDR. Through roundtables in the respective ITAs, the foremost assignment of local actors will be to provide feedback and offer insights as to the robustness and effectiveness of the strategies, frameworks and decision-support tools, as well as on the wider valuation approaches and financing mechanisms to be developed over the course of the project's lifetime. Thus, the Roundtables are foreseen to bring an iterative feedback loop to the research process, with a view to ensure the wider uptake of the project's outcomes and achievements.

Last but not least, local communities in the respective ITAs will be invited to participate in a survey organized both during the early stages and towards the end of the project, as a means to document soil literacy among society thereby bringing insight as to whether the exposure of society to the project's activities on the ground can bring about a strongly desired 'awareness pull' to the benefits to be reaped from healthy soils, thereby leveraging society at large to subscribe to the projects' motto: ISLANDR for Soil Health!

Introduction

The ISLANDR Roadmap is a decision-making tool designed to support users engaged in contaminated site management and land redevelopment. Recognising the complexity of the remediation process, the roadmap does not prescribe a rigid set of steps but instead offers structured guidance to navigate key decisions. While it cannot map every possible choice in advance, it provides a clear direction to help users make informed and effective decisions. Adaptable to different contexts, the roadmap can be tailored to deliver user-specific insights, ensuring relevance and practical value for diverse remediation projects.

The ISLANDR Roadmap aims to support practitioners involved in remediation and redevelopment by leveraging ISLANDR outcomes to add value. The added value provided by ISLANDR project is shown as Building Blocks, dark green coloured boxes linked to the activities of the journey from site identification to maintenance. In some cases, additional Building Blocks derived from other projects have been shown with light green colour. The Roadmap focuses on the nexus between soil health, spatial planning, low-input remediation and wider benefits to strengthen policy and investment cases for the sustainable, risk-based management of “B” and “C” type sites and diffuse contamination. The 2006 CLARINET project report (Ferber et al. 2006) included the “ABC Model” which holds that brownfield sites can be divided into three broad categories based on the financial ease with which they can be reused. For some sites, there is a strong financial feasibility driving redevelopment, for example, because the property value is high, referred to as “Type A”. For some sites, referred to as “Type B”, the Private Sector financial case is marginal, but redevelopment could be facilitated by a public funding intervention such as an investment fund. However, in other cases, there is no direct viable financial case for redevelopment, referred to as “Type C”.

1. Users and journeys

1.1. User groups

Potential user groups involved in remediation and redevelopment the road map might support include site owners, service providers, regional authorities, land developers, regulators, investors and planning authorities among others. Their needs have been considered while developing the roadmap, so four distinct journeys or management pathways were proposed based on the type of site and contamination faced.

1.2. Journey 1: single site

This journey considers remediation / redevelopment / restoration of a single site, that may be contaminated. This single site journey focuses on understanding the level of contamination and exploring different remediation and redevelopment strategies that contribute to build the business case for the actual remediation and redevelopment of the site.

1.3. Journey 2: portfolio of sites

This journey considers a portfolio of sites owned by public or private organisations or by those involved in the privatisation of public sites. The scale of action of this journey is regional/national. It focuses on prioritising sites and finding the synergies to maximise monetary and sustainability gains. For example, private sites (A sites) can finance the redevelopment and remediation of public-private or fully public sites (B and C sites). See explanation of A, B and C sites in the objectives.

1.4. Journey 3: diffuse contamination

This journey considers areas with potential diffuse soil contamination. The scale of action of this journey is regional/national. ISLANDR project defined diffuse soil contamination as a type of soil contamination, that covers large areas, is not necessarily caused by a single contaminant, can be spread via several media to the environment and is typically not originating from a single source or limited to certain industry.

1.5. Caveat

This Roadmap shows the journey in general level. In many detail steps there are alternative approaches in countries. The user is advised to read more from ISLANDR Del6.3 on the implementation on country level.

2. Roadmap components

The roadmap integrates three components: i) phases of the soil remediation process represented by the yellow colour, ii) activities that should take place during each phase, and iii) building blocks that can support the conduction of those activities. There is often no need to go through all the phases but one can go directly to any phase or skip some phases.

2.1. Phases

2.1.1. Identification

The Identification phase marks the initial stage of the ISLANDR Roadmap, where potentially contaminated land areas are identified. This can occur through various pathways, including a strategic inventory process that assesses past site uses, sites entering a spatial planning process with former potential contaminative use; sites with a regulatory demand, or site reviews triggered by events like divestment, mergers, or acquisitions. Additionally, site-specific triggers—such as planned redevelopment, changes in land use, regulatory scrutiny, or external concerns like community complaints or whistleblowing—can also lead to contamination concerns being flagged. This phase sets the foundation for further investigation and decision-making in the remediation process.

2.1.2. Initiative/vision

The Initiative or Vision phase begins with an actor who has an idea of a particular purpose for a site, for example, for housing, business, public amenity, nature, or a combined purpose. The key outcomes of this phase are an initial project champion(s) and an initial vision for a site, which may include a range of future uses. A “vision” for a site may have different levels of detail, ranging simply from an idea and its proponent(s) to a more detailed briefing of the vision and pathway by which it might be reached. In some cases, the use(s) may be interim, which can also support a period of soil health recovery, for example, re-use for photovoltaic electricity in parallel with a nature-based solution. Another form of interim re-use might be linking a long-term treatment opportunity (such as phytoremediation) with interim use, for example, to provide bio feedstock, natural habitat and social amenities via public access or all three. Multiple interim use scenarios are possible.

2.1.3. Planning

The planning phase is the process by which the vision is elaborated to arrive at detailed action plans; master planning, including definition of land uses; investment and business planning; the necessary overarching permissions from regulators, planners and other authorities including spatial planning conditions and permits, process permits, waste permits, verification requirements, institutional controls etc.; the procurement of service providers; allocations of responsibilities, costs, returns, ownerships (including the mode, e.g. freehold, lease, etc.) financial risks and liabilities; community and user engagement. A range of site management activities takes place over this phase including site investigation, risk assessment, risk management planning, remedy selection, remedial design, and verification planning.

2.1.4. Realisation

During this implementation phase, contracts are let, practical delivery activities take place on-site and specific regulatory permissions are agreed upon. The endpoint is the delivery of the vision foreseen in the master planning.

Remediation activities fall within this phase, in some cases in their entirety, including verification (for example, an in situ chemical oxidation treatment) or in others their establishment (for example, a pump and treat system or a phytoremediation).

2.1.5. Maintenance

The scope of maintenance depends on the site context. In some cases, where risk management has been completed, the primary maintenance activity might be institutional control, where the record of site use and risk management is maintained by a planning authority. There will be ongoing monitoring and verification tasks for longer-term treatments, such as natural attenuation, containment, and phytoremediation. For combined re-use and remediation, there may be a variety of business, sustainability information and monitoring collected, for example, related to site re-use.

This phase also encompasses stewardship activities, for example, related to the gradual improvement of soil health.

2.2. ISLANDR General building blocks

There are specific building blocks to support the implementation of several of activities and a cross-cutting building block related to data management:

<p>Building block Guidelines for FAIR data</p>
<p>ISLANDR gives recommendations on a Roadmap to EUSO deliverable to make data on diffuse and local soil contamination Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). To ensure data interoperability, both data and metadata should follow international standards where available.</p> <p>Read more from the Deliverable D1.4 Roadmap to EUSO [Link to D1.4]</p>
<p>Building block Key terminology</p>
<p>For advancing development of standardized data interoperability on for example soil datasets or risk-based land management, harmonising used terminology plays a key role. Soil vocabularies come from many sources (national, international) and when combining data from different source, it needs to have reliable comparison to avoid misinformed decisions. ISLANDR gathered existing soil related vocabularies and proposed an organized list of terms with definitions to have a harmonized terminology for the project. Please find more information on existing vocabularies and standards identified for soil contamination and remediation (Appendix 1) and the terminology used in ISLANDR reports (Appendix 2) from the ISLANDR Deliverable D1.3 Ontology [Link to D1.3].</p>
<p>Building block Overview of local soil contamination databases and other data sources</p>
<p>Overview of local soil contamination databases and other data sources > Support planning and implementing registers/databases suggested in the soil monitoring directive</p> <p>In many states, national and regional authorities have already systematically and actively identified all sites where soil contamination is suspected based on evidence collected through all available means. According to the questionnaire sent to national experts, some countries utilise local soil contamination databases in prioritisation of investigation- and remediation actions of contaminated sites. The web search showed that the site data in many databases contains information of priority classification. National and regional databases feed to European-wide indicator used to assess status of local soil contamination and potentially later to national soil contamination registers as required in Soil Monitoring Law proposal. ISLANDR provides a metadata catalogue of these local (and diffuse) soil contamination databases in Europe. More information at: ISLANDR Deliverable D1.1 Data summary - Overview of Soil Pollution in Europe [Link] The ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue is available from [Link]</p>